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Progression in PBL competences

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ABSTRACT

In engineering education, qualification frameworks as well as curriculum standards, like the CDIO standards, have offered overall guidelines for progression in curriculum design. However, although the development has moved towards more student-centred and active learning environments, the attention towards learning progression specifically focusing on “learning to learn” has been limited.

The scope of this paper is to explore the challenges of creating progression in (problem based learning) PBL competences with a specific focus on the development of meta-cognitive competences. Whereas the conceptual framework builds on the experiential learning theory, the empirical material draws on a study of learning progression at the problem and project organized learning (PBL) institution, Aalborg University. The empirical material includes insights from three engineering domains (Energy, Software and Architecture & Design), and nine focus group interviews with students in their first and third years of the bachelor’s programme and during their master’s study.

The study showed that students develop a more comprehensive understanding of PBL throughout their study as their experience base expands. However, the case also raises attention to the risk of letting PBL competences become embedded into practice to an extent where it becomes tacit. If students do not have a language and a conceptual platform for PBL, it is difficult for them to identify their PBL competences, and it is also hard to transfer their understandings, concepts and methodological framework and apply their PBL competences to new learning situations as well as to new professional contexts.

1 INTRODUCTION

According to Graham [1:39] and based on a study of leaders in engineering education, the future engineering curricula will “*emphasise student choice, multi-disciplinary learning and societal impact, as well as expose students to a breadth of experiences outside the classroom, outside the traditional engineering discipline and across the world*”. Taking this prospect seriously, not many will question the importance of generic competences as an integrated part of the engineering curricula. The question is more related to *how* students should learn and develop these generic competences.

Different educational models have offered frameworks to foster generic competences such as teamwork and communication as well as the ability to cope with real life problems and work across disciplinary boundaries. Most of these models argue for an integrative approach, which means that the progression of generic competences occurs alongside the progression in domain specific competences. This, however, leaves educational designers with the challenge of balancing the concern for both types of competences.

Graham [1:37] points to disciplinary and educational silos as a current barrier for innovation and excellence in engineering education. Furthermore, based on a comprehensive literature review of generic engineering competencies, Male [2:40] concludes “*that academics have difficulties in teaching generic competencies, partly because of the low status assigned to generic competencies in comparison to technical competencies in engineering*”. This paper works under the assumption that a more explicit and conceptual insight on the progression of generic competences is needed in order to understand what is eventually left out due to the aforementioned barriers.

Systemic problem based learning (PBL) models have shown to be effective to foster generic competences [3]. In fact, PBL is developed to co-facilitate generic and domain specific competences by letting students identify, analyse, formulate and solve real life problems, and make a comprehensive assessment of the proposed solutions. In a PBL environment, generic competences are framed and conceptualised as PBL competences.

PBL competences can be characterised by four types of competences: problem-oriented, interpersonal, structural and meta-cognitive [4]. As illustrated in figure 1, the meta-cognitive competences are a cross-cutting competence. As such, meta-competences raise the other competences above the level of application in Bloom’s taxonomy [5], making students able to analyse, evaluate and synthesise their approach to learning to address new modes of applications. As such, without this cross-cutting competence, the other competences are reduced to skills.

Fig. 1. The cross-cutting metacognitive competence together with examples of different competences areas.

With this outset, we initiated a study with the following research question:

What are the challenges of creating progression in PBL competences that includes the cross-cutting meta-cognitive dimension?

2 RESEARCH DESIGN

The research design combines an empirical study of how students relate their study practices to PBL principles with a theoretical perspective on progression based on experiential learning. In the following section, we elaborate on the theoretical framework as well as the methodology of the empirical study.

2.1 Theoretical framework

Whereas taxonomies, like Bloom's taxonomy [5], help to clarify learning levels within the cognitive domain and the corresponding intended learning outcomes, such taxonomies say little about the learning process. Based on a constructivist learning perspective aligned with the roots of PBL, Kolb [6] has offered a model of the learning process (see figure 2).

Kolb (1984) stresses the importance of active learning by stressing active experimentation and concrete experiences as fundamental aspects of learning, but he also stresses the importance of meta-cognitive learning through reflective observation and abstract conceptualization in order to move from the concrete situation to the general and vice versa.

Fig. 2. Illustration of the interaction between the practice dimension and the meta-cognitive dimension of learning based on Kolb's cycle [6].

Like a wheel that needs a shape of a circle to function optimally, the active/situational and the reflective/theoretical sides of the experiential learning circle have to be complete and combined, as indicated in figure 2.

In a progression perspective, Dewey's [7] concepts of continuity and interaction is important in order to transfer the Kolb circle to a continuum of circles. Continuity refers to the way past experiences will influence current experiences. Therefore, learning occurs in a continuum of circles where past experiences will interfere with the way the current experiences are perceived and interpreted. Progression then appears when students build on past experiences in addressing new situations. The concept of interaction nevertheless adds another perspective to the understanding of progression, as interaction refers to situational influence and, thereby, the context of learning. Progression also becomes a matter of the diversity of situations that students face in their education, and in combination with the concept of continuity, their ability to transfer learnings from one context to another.

In terms of curriculum design, continuity stresses the importance of students' ability to build on previous experience (learning depth by addressing similar contexts), whereas interaction stresses the importance of variation (learning width by moving across different contexts).

2.2 Empirical research design

The empirical study has been carried out with the problem based and project organised learning environment at Aalborg University. Since its foundation in 1974, Aalborg University has had a systemic approach to PBL and can therefore, with

reference to the case typology by Flyvbjerg [8], be characterized as an extreme case. The intention is not to generalize the findings, but to highlight that if this challenge is identified even in this case, it is worthwhile to consider in other contexts as well.

The study at Aalborg University was limited to the two engineering faculties: Faculty of Engineering and Science and the Technical Faculty of IT and Design. At these faculties, all students have a 5 ECTS course at the first semester in “Problem-based Learning in Science, Technology and Society”. Apart from the PBL practice during project work supported by facilitators from the disciplines, PBL consultants from PBL research environments scaffold the students to ensure that the students develop meta-cognitive competences. The output of this is that students are to document their meta-cognitive competences through a process-analysis, three times the first year and with increased depth. The process-analysis concept was developed in the late 1990s based on the experiential learning theory, see [9]. However, the systematic development of meta-cognitive PBL competences only takes place during the first year of study.

The data collection was carried out in 2018. The respondent groups were delimited to three engineering domains (Energy, Software and Architecture & Design), and included nine focus group interviews with four to six students each, who were working together on a team project in the first and third year of the bachelor’s programme and during their master’s study.. Aligned with the intention to use an extreme case, coordinating staff from the studies at different levels were contacted to select groups that were considered to have a high level of PBL competence. Focus group interviews with project groups were chosen for students to mutually support each other in their story of the problem based and project organized group work and to get as rich of a picture as possible.

The data-collection instrument was developed from the Aalborg University PBL principles [10]; students at different levels of education were asked to relate their study experiences to these principles, and in the final stage of the interview, students in later semesters were asked to reflect on the progression of PBL competences. The themes of the interview included students’ perspectives on problem-orientation, group collaboration and project management as well as more general perspectives on their learning processes, including aspects of exemplarity, self-directed learning and progression.

In the data-collection phase, young researchers, having experience with qualitative research but limited research experience with PBL, were selected to conduct the interviews with students. It was a deliberate choice to detach the PBL researcher from the discussion in the focus group interviews, and thereby limit PBL concepts and potential assumptions from previous research interfering with the results.

The interviews were recorded and coded in NVivo with respect to the developed understanding of the PBL principles and the sub-categories that unfolded in the empirical material. For this paper, the empirical material was synthesized in order to find material that would inform the specific focus on continuity, interaction and meta-cognitive competences.

3 FINDINGS

In the following, the findings from our study are presented together with a condensed discussion of the potential implications.

3.1 The challenge of combining different types of progression

In the analysis of student responses it becomes clear that some student groups express an understanding of progression which is aligned with the continuity perspective — e.g. going more in depth and developing one's own competences to work with a system (Focus group interview, Energy, Master, 2018):

“In the beginning it (ed: the problem) is more about what we can actually calculate, and then later on it is about whether we can actually improve it — so the problem changes...but it is always a system that we are working on, and the first thing is to understand the system and how we can work with the system. These aspects of how to model a system — we can do that now. So now it is about, how we can improve it.”

In terms of the more structural PBL competences, there are clear indicators of progression based on experiences, as expressed by this student from Software engineering, in his last semester of the bachelor's study:

“Project management is definitely something that gets better the more projects you have experienced, as you experience something that is not functioning on one project and then you know that you have to focus more on that earlier in the next project.”

The students also indicate that continuity can result in an understanding of PBL as a team autonomy. For example, a student in the final year of his bachelor's study in Energy used the metaphor of well-functioning machinery to describe the PBL model:

“As the model is now, it is kind of working on its own because you get together in groups, you form your groups yourselves you are working in the groups and you are having a supervisor — and all the machinery is just functioning really well.”

However, there are also several clear indications of variation in terms of problem design related to different problem types, from more narrow to more open problems, and as always problems relate to different contexts, e.g. systems or user groups. Across programmes, students also highlight company projects as a way of differentiating the problem based project. Below, you find an example of how a student at the end of their bachelor education in Industrial design experienced variation in problem design:

“The way we identify a problem differs. For example, this semester we have to work together with a company. Some go into a company and observe what is happening and based on these observations they define problems. We have instead worked

together with a company who had identified a problem that they wanted us to work with and based on that and the users we have identified our own problem.”

There are less signs of continuity and variation considering the meta-cognitive PBL competences, when we move beyond the first semester. However, a student at the Energy Master level pointed to the part of the PBL experience in the first year that initiated reflection on current practices:

“The primary thing I got out of the PBL course was the part where we reflected on what went well, and what did not go so well....so the reflection part... I could imagine that a similar course could be beneficial after the bachelor level, when we have had more experience with how the projects work...especially if you are not, as we have done, working together with the same people each semester.”

This reflection initiated a discussion in the group in which it became evident that not all students have an interest in PBL subjects, and this was corroborated in other focus group interviews. Therefore, it should be taken into consideration that there can be a motivational barrier to consider when introducing PBL theory to students.

In sum, there is a potential challenge in securing the progression of PBL competences related to the progression of meta-cognitive competences. This raises attention to the integration and continuity of PBL practice and theory.

3.2 The challenge of balancing PBL theory and practice

One student from Industrial design, a first year master's student, exemplified the challenge of combining PBL theory and practice in the following way:

To be honest, I did not get much out of the PBL course we had the first year... it quickly got too general for many of us.”

A peer-student commented:

“It was a little too humanistic and super-academic.”

There appears to be a wish from these students to move PBL away from the abstract and closer to the context of study, but at the same time the very same students also seem to find the different practices within the same PBL institution rather mysterious:

“It is not my impression that what they do in the other programmes is similar to what we do, but it is still PBL”.

The interesting thing is that the students in the first year in the same programme call for more PBL theory in the PBL course in the first semester, pointing towards a potential shift in course-design to be less super-academic. Furthermore, the students pointed to the importance of the course to be taught in a semester where the students can work more freely within their field of study.

The above example demonstrates that even though the students have a PBL course and intensive problem based project work, they do not naturally combine the more abstract with the concrete, although they acknowledge that there is a more generic

nature to PBL. This is a dilemma in learning practice competences that are based on experience combined with theoretical reflection.

There is a need to make PBL more explicit, as so nicely put by one student from Industrial design, a first year master's student:

"I think, more generally, we have just talked about how PBL is deeply rooted in our understanding, but in reality, what is needed is to be more explicit about things. I do not know how..."

It is also the case in other programmes that as PBL theory and the methods presented to optimize PBL practice become known and are partly implemented in practice, they become tacit. A student in the final year of bachelor's study in the Energy programme expresses this in the following way:

"In the first semester, we got a lot of tools, and I do not know how much of it I actually remember, but I think in one way or the other that we use them without really being aware of it."

This perspective is supported by the following quote from a Software master's student, stating that:

"I cannot remember the different elements of the PBL course... but I can remember what it was about, more generally, and I am also quite certain that I have used some of the things I got from that course even though I cannot explicit remember the specifics."

Therefore, it is not that the learnings from the more theoretical side of the Kolb cycle are not brought into practise. The question is, however, how the loop can be closed if the students lack a language to reflect on the experiences and whether a tacit reflection without a subsequent abstract generalisation will be enough when the learning environment changes considerably.

4 CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have focused on the challenges of creating a progression in PBL competences that includes the cross-cutting meta-cognitive dimension. We have chosen the specific focus on meta-cognitive competences to emphasize the process where students explicate, analyse, evaluate, synthesise and optimise their own learning competences. This is seen as a precondition for students to professionally appropriate their ways of learning to new learning contexts, as in future professions.

In the theoretical framework, we underlined the importance of meta-cognitive competences with reference to experiential learning, and the concepts of continuity and interaction were used to distinguish two perspectives on progression. Whereas continuity stresses the importance of students' ability to build on previous experience (learning depth by addressing similar contexts), interaction stresses the importance of variation in the curricula (learning width by moving across different contexts).

Not surprisingly, the empirical study of the extreme case in terms of PBL indicated clear signs of progression in PBL competences. Challenges were, however, detected to create continuity and variation in meta-cognitive competences. As PBL theory, in this specific case, is related to the introductory stages of education, this detachment left students with a tacit understanding of their PBL competences in their later studies. Furthermore, when PBL theory was in play, the alignment of PBL theory with practice and vice versa became crucial, together with an emphasis on motivating students to engage in PBL. The point on motivation indicate that the statement made in the introduction that generic competences is sometimes considered “low status” compared to technical competence also seem to live in pockets of even an extreme case of a PBL institution.

In cases where PBL competences have become tacit and there is a sliding focus on meta-cognitive PBL competences throughout the study, there is a risk that generic PBL competences become a blind spot (not visible within the domain), and even in some cases a black spot (unwanted within the domain). In such situations, strong institutional leadership is needed to unlock potential silo thinking — the kind of thinking which is said to be a remarkable threat to future advances in engineering education.

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